

EUROAGEISM AND U3A

WHAT IS AGEISM?

ONLINE WEBINAR: AGEISM IN MEDIA

Why ageism concerns us all and how we can combat it!

ONLINE WORKSHOP - 26 APRIL 2021. 14H00 CET

Join our webinar series on Ageism in the media, in health care and in the context of technology use. Let's discuss!

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Mass media (e.g. newspapers or social media sites) can be seen as one of the many institutions that contribute to the construction of stereotypical images of ageing and old age. At the same time, the media can play a crucial role in breaking stereotypes and helping to solidify the socially and culturally constructions about older people and late-life. This webinar provides insights into current research on ageism in the mass media. Among other research, an example of ageist discourses around nursing homes during COVID-19 will be discussed.

For more information about EuroAgeism, please visit <https://euroageism.eu/>. You may also email us at info@euroageism.eu

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